

Design and Implementation of Remote Health Monitoring System using IOT with GPS for Prediction and Analysis

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Abstract:- Spontaneous and accurate decisions are needed to care for a critically ill patient so that life-saving and life-saving therapies can be properly applied. Statistics show that one person is losing his life every minute around the world. Many people in India suffer from heart attacks on a daily basis and the main reason for this is that patients lose their lives due to a lack of timely and proper help. This paper is based on patient care. We have developed a reliable, energy-efficient patient screening system. It is able to send parameters to the real-time patient. This doctor is able to actually monitor the patient's health. Here the patient's parameters are constantly calculated and transmitted using IoT. Efforts to increase reliability and flexibility by improving performance and patient care systems provide satisfaction. Currently, the proposed patients are constantly monitored for health and the data is analyzed in a centralized system. Specific parameters of patient health Threshold value If petrol is low, here we are using IoT for inheritance regulatory board. Doctors can find specific information by accessing patient data on their PC, which are constantly updated by the IoT module.

Keywords:- Oximeter sensor, Temp sensor, GPS, IOT Module.

I.INTRODUCTION

Lately, remote sensor networks have been utilized in many examinations to plan remote consideration frameworks. Remote sensor network applications for physiological sign correspondence transmission have numerous advancements. Utilized for physiological sign transmission, like IoT. Even though IoT is utilized for 24-hour checking of the correspondence frameworks, IoT gives high organization adaptability and an enormous number of hubs, and a decent transmission range with low power utilization empowers the extension of such frameworks to countless hubs.

As of late, IoT-based remote organizations have been tried in different applications. The proposed patient IoT observing framework will be helpful or valuable for clinical experts to proper and treat, as well as further develop illness for the executives of medical services suppliers. The patient is observed and the information is moved to the PC and used to record the patient's side effects.

II.LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Paper1 -- Md. Raseduzzaman Ruman Retrieved on: 2020 "IoT Based Emergency Health Monitoring System".

In these ten years, IoT-based frameworks assume a significant part in clinical gadgets. Thus, numerous scientists are attempting to foster different IoT-based clinical gadgets. Crafted by certain specialists are given beneath; One analyst executed a patient checking framework to gather information for clinical exploration and instructive investigations. PHS will empower quicker and more secure preventive consideration, lower generally speaking expenses, worked on persistent focused practice, and improved solidness. In this paper, the specialists executed a framework that screens body boundaries, for example, beat rate and ECG. The ARM7LPC 2138 processor is utilized as the principle interface and the information is shown utilizing the graphical UI is shipped off the versatile through SMS assuming any boundaries fall inside the ordinary reach. This work depicts an electronic gadget that screens the strength of the old in their own home with the assistance of remote sensor innovation. A far-off medical services framework screens a patient's wellbeing status utilizing clinical benefit supplier hardware.

B. Paper2 -- "An IoT-based Patient Health Monitoring System" 2018.

In this paper, the Medical care climate has created science and information given remote detecting hub innovation. Patients need to manage the issue of surprising passing because of heart issues and explicit reasons for the assault, which are because of the way that patients don't get appropriate clinical consideration at the expected time. This is particularly valid for old patients and specialists and friends and family. So we are proposing an inventive undertaking to diminish such unplanned passing utilizing patient wellbeing checking that utilizes sensor innovation and utilizations the Web to speak with friends and family assuming issues emerge. The framework utilizes temperature and pulse sensors to follow the patient's wellbeing. The two sensors are associated with the Arduino-Uno. The information is shipped off a web server (remote detecting hub) by interacting with a miniature regulator with an LCD show and Wi-Fi association to track the patient's wellbeing. Directions are shipped off the patient involving IoT in the event of unexpected change in the patient's pulse or internal heat level. The framework additionally shows live information of patients' temperature and pulse alongside timestamps on the Web.

C. Paper3 -- Tarannum Khan, Manju K. Chattopadhyay.: 'SMART HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM', IEEE.

This administrative work presents A brilliant wellbeing observing framework that utilizes biomedical sensors to look at a patient's condition and uses the Internet to illuminate those concerned. Biomedical sensors are associated with the Arduino UNO regulator to peruse the information communicated with LCD show/chronic screen for review of the result. The information is transferred to the server for capacity and changed over to a JSON interface for representation on the cell phone. The Android application is intended to make patient data effectively available to their primary care physicians and relatives.

D. Paper4 -- "Internet of Thing Based Healthcare Monitoring System" IEEE.

In this paper, the plan and improvement of ZigBee-based wearable physiological boundaries observing gadget is created and revealed. This framework can be utilized to screen physiological boundaries, for example, pulse and human internal heat level. The task expects to fabricate and work a dependable, reasonable, low energy, and exact framework that can be worn consistently and screen key highlights in light of Zigbee innovation. The gadget recognizes whether an individual is therapeutically troubled and the beneficiary unit is associated with the PC's plot chart for the noticed actual boundaries of the human body. Brought together tolerant consideration frameworks are popular because they decrease work expenses and expenses as well as lessen clinical hospitalization time. In the past wired correspondence was utilized yet presently Zigbee with remote cross-section is liked as it decreases the expense. ZigBee is likewise liked over Bluetooth and infrared remote correspondence because of its low energy effectiveness and long reach.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The ordinary internal heat level of a sound, resting grown-up is 98.6 degrees or Fahrenheit 37.0 degrees Celsius. Albeit the internal heat level estimated on an individual can shift, a sound human internal heat level is around 37.0 degrees Celsius.

Biomedical gadgets innovation takes you past the essentials of hardware and power to the universe of cutting-edge mechanical frameworks connected with clinical consideration. This program will be important to you Develop the abilities and reasonable foundation expected to assess, test, adjust and fix progressed clinical hardware and apparatuses, and secure the relational abilities expected to work with clinical faculty. Research valuable open doors are accessible in emergency clinics, clinical hardware organizations, and other clinical offices.

IV. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig. 1: Block Diagram of a Health Care Monitoring System

A. Pulse Sensor

The pulse sensor is a reflection-type photoelectric analog sensor used to measure pulse and heart rate. When the finger is inserted, the sensor can transmit the collected analog signal to the MCU. And then the analog signal will be converted to a digital signal. Upon completion of a simple calculation, the MCU receives heart rate values and uploads them to a computer.

Fig. 2: Pulse sensor

B. Temperature Sensor

This is a sensor used to measure temperature. The LM35 series are precision integrated-circuit temperature sensors, whose output voltage is more precisely linear than the temperature at Celsius (centigrade) than thermistors. It is sealed and does not oxidize. No need to increase the output voltage.

Fig. 3: Temperature Sensor

C. Oxygen Sensor

A pulse oximeter is used to continuously measure oxygen in the blood. The use of IoT with pulse oximetry is useful for technical use.

D. Bpm Sensor

High blood pressure indicates that the heart is pumping vigorously through the body. The IoT method promotes the diagnosis and treatment of health problems, including high blood pressure (BP) and hemoglobin(HB).

E. LCD Display

The 16x2 LCD display is a very basic module and is commonly used in various equipment and circuits. 16x2 LCD means it can display 16 characters in each line and there are 2 such lines.

Fig. 4: 16*2 LCD Display

F. GPS Module

The GPS module calculates the position of any patient by identifying the signals transmitted by the satellites. The GPS receiver measures the distance of each satellite and the raw data is converted into latitude, longitude. Used to measure altitude speed and time.

Fig. 5: GPS Module

G. IoT Module

An IoT Module is a small electronic device embedded in objects and things connected to wireless networks and sends and received data.

V.CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig. 6: Circuit Diagram of a Health Monitoring System

This circuit is based on patient care. We have designed and developed a reliable, energy-efficient patient monitoring system. It is able to send the patient's parameters in real-time. Here the patient's parameters are constantly measured and transmitted wirelessly using IoT. Uses a displacement transducer for respiratory rate sensing using an oximeter sensor. and oximeter senses the sensed oxygen level and Pulse sensor used for a checked pulse rate of the human body and also checked Blood pressure its shown the heart pumping through the body powerfully and the parameter to the 16*2 display. Atmega328 controller through all parameters is converted analog to digital converted data format and shown to the 16*2 display. The panic switch is used for emergency purposes if anyone parameter does not give the proper reading or if an emergency situation arises then a panic switch through message will be sent to nearby people and Hospital. GPS through will be able to find out where the sick person is and provided immediate care to save his life.

VI.FEATURE SCOPE

It will be used to generate the hospital network by providing the facility and expert instantly from a remote location. This system will be able to provide the correct test reports, advice, prescription, provide various details that one wants to know about this health from the doctor from being far away/remotely. Provided the parameters on the system.

It will ensure contactless treatment, enhancing both the doctor and patient safety. It would also be accessible to remote as well places of far distance and out of reach in the case of emergency wherein physical access is not possible.

VII. CONCLUSION

To computerize the work of the hospital. The software caters to all the needs of the average hospital and is capable of providing easy and efficient storage of information related to the patients visiting the hospital. It generates test reports, provides prescription details along with various tests, dietary advice, and prescription drugs to patients and doctors. It also provides reliable billing facilities to the patient, whether at home or outpatient. The system also provides backup facilities as required.

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